

Potentiometric Studies on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Gallium(III) and Indium(III) with Ethylenediaminediacetic Acid as Primary Ligand

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Potentiometric studies on some mixed ligand complexes of Ga(III) and In(III) using ethylenediaminediacetic acid as primary ligand and oxalic acid, malonic acid, succinic acid, maleic acid, malic acid, itaconic acid, pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid, pyrocatechol, resorcinol or phthalic acid as secondary ligand have been reported. $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ have been evaluated at three different temperatures and at an ionic strength $\mu=0.2 M$. The results are correlated on the basis of steric and structural characteristics of the chelates formed.

ALTHOUGH considerable work has been done on the mixed ligand complex formation of heavier metals¹⁻⁵, such complexes of Ga(III) and In(III) are comparatively less explored. In our previous communication⁶, mixed ligand complex forming tendency of Ga(III) using nitrilotriacetic acid as primary ligand was discussed. The present paper describes the results obtained on the study of some mixed ligand complexes of Ga(III) and In(III) using ethylenediaminediacetic acid (EDDA) as primary ligand and oxalic acid (OXA), malonic acid (MLA), succinic acid (SUC), maleic acid (MAE), malic acid (MA), itaconic acid (ITCA), pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (PDCA), pyrocatechol (PYC), resorcinol (RES) or phthalic acid (PTHA) as secondary ligand. The formation constants, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, have been determined by the modified method of Irving and Rossotti⁷ at 15, 30 and 45° and at ionic strength, $\mu=0.2 M$ (NaClO₄).

The necessary condition for the study of mixed ligand complexes by the present method is that the formation of the 1 : 1 primary complex, MA, should be complete at lower pH and it should be stable upto the higher pH where the secondary ligand combines with the primary complex. This condition holds good in the present study. The $\log K$ values for [Ga(III)-EDDA] primary complex is 12.3 and that of [In(III)-EDDA] primary complex is 10.5. The tendencies of these chelates to bind an additional secondary ligand were measured which revealed that EDDA occupies four coordination positions around Ga(III) or In(III) ion and leaves behind two coordination positions for incoming bidentate secondary ligand^{8,9}. The coordination number attained by Ga(III) and In(III) in the formation of mixed ligand complexes in the present study is therefore six and no further expansion of coordination number is observed.

Experimental

A stock solution of 0.02 *M* of Ga(NO₃)₃.XH₂O and In(NO₃)₃.6H₂O was prepared by dissolving the requisite amounts in a calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis of the metal salt. The metal content was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating their 8-hydroxyquinolates¹⁰. Stock solution of 0.01 *M* EDDA was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity in double distilled water and was estimated potentiometrically. 0.2 *M* perchloric acid, 2.0 *M* sodium perchlorate and 0.01 *M* solutions of OXA (BDH), MLA (Riedel), SUC (BDH), MAE (Riedel), MA (E. Merck), ITCA (BDH), PDCA (BDH) and PTHA (BDH) were prepared in double distilled water and estimated potentiometrically. 0.01 *M* solutions of PYC (Riedel) and RES (Sisco) were prepared in purified ethanol by directly weighing the purified sample. Carbonate free solution of standard sodium hydroxide was prepared by standard method¹¹.

An Ecil expanded scale pH-meter fitted with glass-calomel electrode assembly, with an accuracy of ± 0.02 pH unit was used to measure [H⁺] of the solution. The saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of an agar bridge saturated with KNO₃ to prevent formation of chloro complexes. The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen during the course of experiments. The temperature was maintained constant with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ with the help of U-10 thermostat.

For determining the stability constants ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$), four mixtures were prepared as follows.

- (i) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid.
- (ii) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

(iii) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ EDDA + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ga(III) or In(III) solution.

(iv) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ EDDA + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Ga(III) or In(III) solution + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

These four mixtures were prepared in such a manner that the concentration of common ingredients were identical in each mixture. The ionic strength was kept constant by adding appropriate amount of neutral NaClO_4 solution. The total volume of each of the four mixtures was kept identical by adding double distilled water. In case of RES and PYC these mixtures were prepared in 50% (v/v) ethanol. The mixtures were titrated pH-metrically against standard NaOH and graphs between pH-meter reading and volume of alkali added were plotted. The four titration curves so obtained were referred to as (i) acid curve, (ii) secondary ligand curve, (iii) primary complexation curve and (iv) mixed ligand complexation curve.

Proton-ligand stability constants :

The 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants of the secondary ligands used have been evaluated at three different temperatures by the method of Irving and Rossotti. A graph was plotted between \bar{n}_A and pH and the practical proton-ligand stability constants were evaluated by employing (A) the method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A value and (B) the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. The values of first proton-ligand stability constant $\log K_1^H$ with an error limit of ± 0.05 and second proton-ligand stability constant $\log K_2^H$ with an error limit of ± 0.07 at three different temperatures and fixed ionic strength of $0.2 M$ (NaClO_4) are reported in Table 1.

Metal-ligand stability constants :

The formation of mixed ligand complex is revealed from the increase in pH of precipitation of mixed ligand complex when compared with the pH of precipitation of primary complex alone and the horizontal difference $[(V_4 - V_3) - (V_2 - V_1)]$ from which \bar{n} is calculated. These V_1, V_2, V_3 and V_4 are volumes of NaOH required for reaching the same pH for titration of mixtures (i), (ii), (iii) and (iv), respectively.

During the formation of primary complex two protons are released which indicates that both the carboxylic groups of EDDA participate in complexation. The nature of the curves also reveals the complete formation of 1 : 1 complex [Ga(III)-EDDA] upto pH 2.7 {pH 3.0 for [In(III)-EDDA] complex}. This complex is stable upto pH 5.5 {pH 5.0 for In(III)-EDDA} complex after which it dissociates and forms metal hydroxide. Thus the mixed ligand complex formation takes place after pH 3.0 and the pH of precipitation is shifted to ≈ 6.5 . The values of stability constants were computed by two methods : (A) interpolation at half \bar{n} value and (B) interpolation at various \bar{n} values. The stability

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGANDS

($\mu = 0.2 M \text{NaClO}_4$)

Ligand	Constants	Temp. °C					
		15		30		45	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
OXA	$\log K_1^H$	3.93	3.95	3.88	3.90	3.82	3.84
	$\log K_2^H$	1.86	1.85	1.80	1.81	1.74	1.74
MLA	$\log K_1^H$	5.15	5.17	5.12	5.15	5.09	5.10
	$\log K_2^H$	3.42	3.40	3.38	3.36	3.32	3.31
SUC	$\log K_1^H$	5.22	5.20	5.16	5.15	5.10	5.09
	$\log K_2^H$	4.13	4.12	4.10	4.11	4.09	4.07
MAE	$\log K_1^H$	5.72	5.70	5.68	5.65	5.62	5.60
	$\log K_2^H$	3.08	3.09	3.02	3.03	3.00	3.01
MA	$\log K_1^H$	4.64	4.62	4.60	4.58	4.56	4.55
	$\log K_2^H$	3.44	3.42	3.40	3.38	3.34	3.33
ITCA	$\log K_1^H$	5.28	5.25	5.22	5.20	5.18	5.15
	$\log K_2^H$	3.92	3.90	3.90	3.89	3.88	3.87
PDCA	$\log K_1^H$	5.18	5.20	5.10	5.12	5.03	5.05
	$\log K_2^H$	3.36	3.38	3.30	3.31	3.26	3.27
PYC*	$\log K_1^H$	11.72	11.73	11.60	11.61	11.45	11.47
	$\log K_2^H$	8.80	8.78	8.72	8.70	8.65	8.62
RES*	$\log K_1^H$	11.78	11.75	11.70	11.67	11.61	11.58
	$\log K_2^H$	8.97	8.99	8.92	8.95	8.86	8.90
PTHA	$\log K_1^H$	4.62	4.65	4.55	4.57	4.48	4.50
	$\log K_2^H$	2.25	2.21	2.21	2.18	2.18	2.14

*Experiments in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

($\mu = 0.2 M \text{NaClO}_4$)

Systems	Temp. °C					
	15		30		45	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(OXA)]	4.90	4.87	4.82	4.79	4.72	4.73
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(MLA)]	5.90	5.93	5.86	5.90	5.81	5.85
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(SUC)]	5.04	5.07	4.96	4.95	4.90	4.92
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(MAE)]	6.34	6.32	6.30	6.26	6.25	6.21
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(MA)]	4.70	4.71	4.65	4.67	4.60	4.65
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(ITCA)]	3.90	3.93	3.80	3.81	3.72	3.69
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(PDCA)]	4.33	4.37	4.30	4.33	4.26	4.28
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(PYC)]*	7.36	7.39	7.31	7.30	7.26	7.29
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(RES)]*	6.45	6.49	6.40	6.43	6.36	6.38
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(PTHA)]	6.30	6.33	6.22	6.26	6.12	6.15
[Ga(III)-(EDDA)-(OXA)]	4.60	4.61	4.54	4.53	4.48	4.49
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(MLA)]	5.45	5.45	5.39	5.40	5.34	5.36
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(SUC)]	4.70	4.71	4.64	4.65	4.58	4.60
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(MAE)]	6.26	6.27	6.20	6.19	6.14	6.12
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(MA)]	4.55	4.53	4.51	4.49	4.47	4.45
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(ITCA)]	4.05	4.08	3.95	3.97	3.90	3.92
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(PDCA)]	4.02	4.00	3.98	3.96	3.95	3.93
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(PYC)]*	6.46	6.49	6.40	6.42	6.34	6.35
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(RES)]*	6.03	6.01	5.99	5.98	5.95	5.92
[In(III)-(EDDA)-(PTHA)]	5.88	5.90	5.80	5.82	5.72	5.74

*Experiments in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture.

constants at three different temperatures and constant ionic strength of $0.2 M \text{NaClO}_4$ with an error limit of ± 0.08 are summarised in Table 2 for

[Ga(III)-EDDA-secondary ligand] and [In(III)-EDDA-secondary ligand] complexes.

Discussion

The primary ligand EDDA (A) occupies four coordination positions around Ga(III) or In(III) as it is tetradentate in nature. Thus, after the formation of 1:1 primary complex there are two coordination positions vacant for incoming bidentate secondary ligand (L) to satisfy the characteristic coordination number six. The formation of mixed ligand complex greatly enhances the stability of the chelate and decreases the tendency of the chelate compound to hydrolyse.

The stability of the mixed ligand complex, MAL, is expected to be less than the binary complexes MA with primary ligand or ML with secondary ligand. This is because of the fact that in the formation of mixed ligand complex, the secondary ligand approaches a unipositive primary complex with lesser number of coordination positions vacant in metal ion for its own attachment. However, in the formation of binary complexes all the coordination positions of metal are vacant and the metal ion is tripositively charged. So, from the statistical and electrostatic points of view the stability constant value for MA or ML is more than that of MAL which is found to be true in the present case also.

The stability of the mixed ligand complex is mainly governed by the characteristics of the approaching secondary ligand. In case of aliphatic carboxylic acids the stability constants were found to be in the order MAE > MLA > SUC > MA > OXA > ITCA. This trend can be justified on the basis of ring size of chelate and structural and donor characteristics of the ligand molecule. OXA forms five-membered ring, MLA six-membered while SUC, MA, MAE and ITCA form seven-membered chelate rings. However, lower stability of OXA might be due to extrastability of OXA anion due to resonance which results in lowering of its complexing tendency. The higher stability of MAE chelate might be due to

conjugate double bond of the ligand which increases the stability due to exocyclic conjugation. The order of stability in seven-membered chelate rings is MAE > SUC > MA > ITCA. The lower stability of ITCA might be due to the presence of =CH₂ group which is electron donating in nature, while the -OH group present in MA decreases basicity of ligand due to its electron withdrawing nature.

In Ga(III) and In(III), the ligands having oxygen donors form more stable complexes than ligands with nitrogen donors. Thus even though PDCA forms five-membered ring it forms less stable chelate as compared to six-membered chelate ring of PTHA. Between PYC and RES, the former forms more stable complex than the latter because PYC forms five-membered chelate ring and RES forms six-membered.

On comparing the stabilities of Ga(III) and In(III) with similar ligands, it is found that Ga(III) complexes are more stable than In(III) complexes. This is the expected trend due to smaller ionic radius of Ga(III).

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